

NATIONAL-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING THE MEANING OF DESIRE (IN PROVERBS)

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Abstract. In the article, an attempt was made to analyze the national-cultural characteristics of lexical units expressing desire in English and Uzbek using phraseological units, especially proverbs. Tradition - customs, way of life, culture were highlighted in the analysis of proverbs.

Keywords: national tradition, language, history, literature, linguo-cultural science, lingvoculturema, national-cultural characteristics, concept, proverb.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНО-КУЛЬТУРНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ, ВЫРАЖАЮЩИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЖЕЛАНИЯ (В ПОСЛОВИЦАХ)

Аннотация. В статье предпринята попытка анализа национально-культурных особенностей лексических единиц, выражающих желание, в английском и узбекском языках с использованием фразеологизмов, прежде всего пословиц. При анализе пословиц освещались традиции - обычаи, быт, культура.

Ключевые слова: национальная традиция, язык, история, литература, лингвокультурология, лингвокультурема, национально-культурные особенности, концепт, пословица.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, knowing and learning a foreign languages has become the most important require of these days. Every person belongs to a specific culture, which includes national traditions, language, history, and literature. Economic, cultural and scientific relations between countries led to the interpretation of language as a tool that reflects culture. As E. Sepir noted, language is a guiding tool in the study of culture [6,8].

When one learning a language, it is not enough to know only words and communication, but also the culture, worldview, lifestyle, and customs of the country where the language is being studied. This, in turn, led to the appear of a new field in linguistics, that is, linguistic and cultural studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The task of linguistics and culture is to study the relationship between language and culture, the reflection of culture in language, and intercultural communication. The main concept of linguocultural studies is lingvoculturema.

Lingvoculturema is a language or speech unit that reflects a part of culture in its semantics (meaning) [1,67]. Lingvoculturema include words that reflect a part of culture (root, artificial, compound and complex words), phraseological units, word combinations, sentences, paremies, speech clichés, complex syntactic units, texts, including folklore texts, etc. Lingvoculturema has a plan of meaning and expression The expression plan is made up of the above-mentioned units, and the meaning plan is made up of the semantics of those units. So, lingvoculturema differs from the concept in that it is a language or speech unit, and has a plan of expression and meaning.

V.A. Maslova emphasizes the existence of 9 types of linguoculturema:

1. Vocabulary without equivalent; 2. Mythological language units; 3. Paremiological foundation of the language; 4. Phraseological foundation of the language; 5. Symbols, stereotypes; 6. Metaphor and language images; 7. Stylistic content of the language; 8. Speech behavior; 9. Speech etiquette. Therefore, among the current units, the lexical units separated by the meaning of desire gained special importance for us [2,18].

RESULTS

In the article, we used phraseological units, especially proverbs, in researching the national-cultural characteristics of lexical units expressing the meaning of desire in the English and Uzbek languages. Because phraseological units are inextricably linked with the distant and recent past, customs and current way of life and aspirations of the people who speak that language. It is in the phraseological units that the national-cultural characteristics of that people are clearly manifested. Therefore, national-cultural characteristics represent the uniqueness of each nation.

For example, "Want of wit is worse than want of wealth" in English corresponds to proverbs in Uzbek "Илм олиш – нина билан қудуқ қазил демак", and "Иди в науку – терпеть муку" in Russian. . This proverb is an assessment given to intelligent people in the language being compared since ancient times, and it is aimed at people who want to conduct scientific activities. As we know from history, carrying out scientific activities and creativity is a very complicated process that requires a lot of effort. Our people have always honored intellectuals and are still honoring them.

Another example: "Want is the mother of industry." This proverb applies to people who are trying to get knowledge and corresponds to the Uzbek proverbs "Тиришганинг тўқмоғи тошга чега қоқар" and Russian proverbs "Голь на выдумки хитра" The proverb involved in the analysis also means the value given to intelligent people since ancient times, that is, the meaning of desire for knowledge.

DISCUSSION

English proverb "Where there is a will there is a way" corresponds to in Uzbek "Интиланга толе ёр" and in Russian "Где хотеёе, там и уменье".

We can clearly see that hardworking is glorified in the compared languages.

The same meaning can be found in the following proverbs:

"If you touch pot, you must touch penny" The alternative in Uzbek is "Текинга мушук хам офтобга чикмайди"; in Russian, this proverb corresponds to : "Даром ничего не даётся".

CONCLUSIONS

According to the results of our analysis and many opinions and views of our mentioned above scholar, all the proverbs involved the traditions, customs, way of life, and culture of the people of the compared languages. Therefore, the lack of comprehensive study of the category of desire and the presence of different opinions and views still require a lot of scientific research.

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